

Research Article

The Effect of Parents' Level of Education on Pupils' Academic Performance in Public Primary Schools in Western Area Urban District, Sierra Leone

^aGeorge Tony Patrick and ^bUmar Sorie Fofanah

^{a&b}Department of Teacher Education, School of Education, Njala University, Sierra Leone

*Corresponding Author Email: tonyp.george@njala.edu.sl

Received: October 13, 2024

Accepted: November 04, 2024

Published: November 12, 2024

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to unearth the effect of parents' level of education on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in western area urban. The study targets an estimated number of (60) parents, teachers, and pupils drawn from (5) primary schools in the western area urban. A purposive sampling technique was used to examine the total population of parents, teachers, and pupils in the survey. The findings of the study show that most parents were living in overcrowded homes, and they found it difficult to meet their physical and emotional needs to support and positively influence the academic performance of pupils in primary schools in the western area urban district. The findings further indicated that the majority of the parents had only secondary education. This implies that the education of parents has a significant influence on pupils' academic performance. The study recommends that the Ministry of Basic and Senior Secondary Education (MBSSE) and the Freetown Municipal Council, provide remedial adult education classes to improve the skills and knowledge of parents in order to build their capacities. The government through the Ministry of Land Housing and Country Planning builds more estates for parents at a cost recovery that meets the needs of a parent living in overcrowded homes.

Keywords: Education, Academic Performance, Parents, Teachers, Primary Schools.

1. Introduction

Raya (2018), in his study focusing at children's academic performance found out that, there was association between parent's education with children's academic achievement mediated by the home environment. In developed countries, research findings from both adults' education and early childhood intervention programme note that the parent level of education is one of the most important factors influencing children reading level and other school achievements (Niklas *et al.*, 2016). More highly educated parents have greater success in providing their children with cognitive and language skills that contribute to early success in schools (Chen *et al.*, 2018).

Tan *et al.*, (2020) also found that maternal education had the most consistent direct influence on children's cognitive outcomes. Therefore, this makes those pupils to achieve higher than those whose parents are of low education level. In the same view, Hirsch (2019) argues that, households with higher level of education stress on the importance of education for their children because they perceive education as a tool for overcoming ignorance and poverty. The study indicated that, literate parents focus more on giving their children education and hence spend time on helping their children with their homework and checking what their children have learned at school. The evidence suggests that literate parents follow closer their children academic progress by purchasing books, monitoring their children and providing stimulating experience (Mauka, 2015). These contribute to pupils' achievement.

Mothers who are more educated and have higher self-esteem have children who receive higher test scores (Akinbode and Olasunkanmi, 2016). Liu (2015) concluded that eight grader aspirations to attend college derive primary from parents' education. Other researchers found substantial support for positive relationship between mothers' and fathers' supportive behavior, educational level, language spoken in the home and adolescent's aspirations (Paat, 2017).

In Sierra Leone, it has been established that poor families are more likely to be illiterate. Illiterate parents are not spending money on their children's education as compared to their better-off counterparts (Anthony, 2019). Parents with a low level of primary education are the ones who are illiterate and do not value education much. To the contrary, qualified parents are more likely to value education (Erola *et al.*, 2016) found that at least half the variance in educational attainment was attributed to family background, including parental schooling. The above observation is consolidated by Arthur (2022) who studied the impact of the parental socioeconomic status on the academic achievement in secondary schools. In Tanzania, he established that the parents with high academic qualification and formal occupation know the importance of education to their children and they were not reluctant to support them in paying fees, buying books and provision of funds for remedial classes known as tuition.

Numerous studies have underscored the significance of establishing strong connections between the home and school (Nzuruba, 2024). Parents' education is such a motivating force for a child which paves the way for his/her future. It is an admitted fact that the children of educated parents are more confident, resourceful, and experienced than the children whose parents lack education. The primary responsibility of parents is to ensure their children's school attendance and completion of assignments (MacDonald, 2019). However, as noted by these researchers, many parents lack formal education and are illiterate in basic subjects such as math, reading, and writing (Idris *et al.*, 2020). Bakar *et al.*, (2017) conducted a study on the ways in which students' academic achievements are affected by parental education and their socio-economic status. Participants were 250 pupils taken from randomly selected departments and research findings are to be generalized to the University of Sargodha pupils. Pupils were selected from MA 3rd level with the demographic information of gender, role number and department. Data is collected from participants through a questionnaire which contains three basic variables. Parental education and socio-economic status are independent variables and student's achievement is dependent variable. Analysis of data indicates that pupils belonging to strong financial status perform better than those who face problems in finance. Similarly, parental education boosts their children's performance.

Paweenawat (2024) indicated a connection between parental education and children's academic success, emphasizing that this impact might differ based on gender. Unlike the study that explored the influence of parental education on both male and female children within the same household, the current investigation will not focus on gender disparities. Instead, it will analyze the educational outcomes of all learners. Anderson (2018) suggested that a higher level of parental education and stable income positively correlate with children's educational advantage over peers whose parents have lower income, limited education, or semi-literacy. They argued that well-educated parents are more likely to provide an enriched educational environment, driven by their superior education and financial stability.

Kiboi (2018) conducted research that highlighted the commitment of highly educated parents toward their children's education, both in terms of time and financial resources. The study revealed a link between family income and academic achievements. Consequently, parents with higher educational backgrounds often possess the means to invest in resources like expensive private tuition, teaching materials, and other educational aids. While this study sheds light on these connections, there remains a gap in understanding the influence of parental education on their children's academic performance. Parents who possess higher education than their children may recognize the value of providing intellectually stimulating activities, serving as a significant motivator. The educational achievements of pupils are substantially influenced by the educational involvement of parents, reflecting the wider significance of parental engagement in educational success (Castro *et al.*, 2015). Ali *et al.*, (2023) conducted research exploring the correlation between parental education levels and their children's educational achievements in a town in South Punjab, Pakistan. The outcomes demonstrated a strong positive association between parents' educational attainment and their children's intellectual success.

Das and Tiwari (2023) conducted a Norwegian study investigating the impact of parental educational backgrounds on their children's educational progress. The study revealed a positive correlation between parents' educational levels and their children's academic success. The academic achievements of pupils are closely intertwined with the educational attainment of their parents. Educated parents are more likely to be engaged in their child's education, including assisting with homework. Regardless of the setting, educated parents tend to invest in extra stationery and school supplies to enhance the learning environment and performance. Children with parents who have low educational aspirations may face challenges in terms of school readiness (Muthomi, 2019). Otieno (2019) conducted a study on the influence and impact of parents' educational level on pupils' academic achievement at secondary level of education. The study utilizes the

pupils' results of the 9th class in secondary school certificate examination taken by the Board of Intermediate and Secondary Education Dera Ghazi Khan. The study found out the impact of parental education status on pupils' academic achievements at secondary school level. The research population was the pupils of different public and private high schools of District Rajanpur, South Punjab. 200 pupils of grade 10th were taken as a sample randomly. After analysis of the data the research finds a significant positive relationship between parents' education level and academic achievements of pupils. Davis-Kean *et al.*, (2019) concluded that parental beliefs, education levels, and salaries significantly predicted academic achievements. Studies investigating the correlation between mothers' educational attainment and pupils' performance found that the mother's education had a more substantial impact on academic success than the fathers. However, these studies were conducted in Western nations, leaving a knowledge gap concerning the influence of household characteristics in the suggested location (Magnuson, and Duncan, 2019).

According to Mwakililo and Mgaya (2021) home set up such as space, furniture (chairs and tables), home chores distribution, silence and reading rooms provide encouragements for the pupils to take studies at home thus contribute to better academic achievements. Malumo (2020) also consolidates the above observation on the roles of the parents in facilitating pupils' academic achievement when established that the heavy agricultural work at home, bricks making and involvement in the petty businesses among the pupils hindered academic performance among the secondary pupils in Kinondoni District Council. According to Dave's model developed by Kikoti (2018) shows five aspects of home environment that influence the academic performance of a child. Bloom identifies five home environment processes namely: Work habits' of the family, which refers to degree of structure and routine in home management and the emphasis or lack of it in educational activities over leisure activities after school hours and during holiday. Secondly, academic guidance and support which include parents' frequent encouragement on schoolwork and their knowledge of pupils' progress at school. The ability and quality of help provided by home for school related tasks includes adequate space and time for revision, relevant guidance and availability of learning materials. Thirdly, intellectual stimulation which is done by family members to provide intellectual interest to the pupils, for example, the type of reading which is done, the nature and extent of conversation about ideas, and nature of intellectual model which parents provide. Fourthly, language model and quality of language used by the parents and taught, either direct or indirectly to the child. Lastly, is academic aspiration and expectation which includes the parents' knowledge on the pupils' current schoolwork and the parents' aspirations for the standard of the children educational achievement.

Similarly, Puccioni (2015) argues that, most of children who are successful and well-adjusted come from home environment where good relationships exist between children and their parents, so parental involvement is much more likely to promote pupils school success when it occurs in the context of consistent home environment. Whether parents are helping and support their children school life can directly affect their personal and social development as well as their academic success (Mwakililo and Mgaya, 2021). This is to say, parental involvement makes a positive contribution to children's educational achievement. Epstein (2019) argues that pupils at all grade levels do better academic work and have more positive school attitudes, higher aspirations, and other positive behaviors if they have parents who are aware, knowledgeable, encouraging, and involved. In his study Lazaro (2023) in assessing pupils' performance focusing at home environment indicated that, schools need more involvement from parents since the chief benefits on their children's education are higher grades, positive behavior and attitude and more effective schools. According to Wakiuru (2016) parental involvement in their children's education takes on various forms. For instance, parents may be involved by volunteering at school, communicating with the school, participation in school decision-making, or supporting learning at home. According to Strickland (2015), parents agree that they have an important role to play in home-based activities when it comes to children's learning. These home-based activities include, among others, monitoring their child's school work and progress, discussing school related issues with their child, and assisting with homework.

In a study conducted by Núñez *et al.*, (2017) revealed that 95% of pupils reported that they performed highly in school at least some of the time when they received help with homework from their parents. Studies have shown marked improvement in pupils' academic achievement when their parents are involved with their homework (Yahaya *et al.*, 2020). Readiness for school learning especially performance at secondary level depend much on home set up, the home activities, motivation by parents availability of relevant extra reading materials in the form of text books and kind of guidance available at home. Also, frequency communication is required between school staff and parents to discuss ways to help their children. However, evidence suggests the most of these contacts are often school initiated (Kigobe *et al.*, 2021).

2. Methodology

The study used the survey design as it entailed the collection of qualitative and quantitative data from the various respondents at the same time. This study adopted descriptive research design. Descriptive research design is a plan, a roadmap and blueprint strategy of investigation conceived so as to obtain answers to research objectives; it is the heart of any study (Rukwaru, 2015). The study used this design because it looks at the phenomena, events and issues the way they are (Onwuegbuzie and Collins, 2017). This design is used because it examines the problem at hand thoroughly to define it, clarify it and obtain pertinent information that can be of use to people in the education sector. The design is good in generalization of the results and it is easy to administer and record answers.

2.1. Data Collection Methods and Instruments: Questionnaires were administered to 10 pupils, 40 parents and 10 teachers. This means the sample constituted 60 respondents. This instrument was used basically due to its capacity to collect a lot of information from a large number of respondents and within a short period of time. The instrument is useful because of its ability to collect the data beyond the physical reach of the observer (Badore, 2018). A questionnaire is essentially a structured technique for collecting primary data. It is generally a series of written questions for which the respondents have to provide the answers (Kapur, 2018).

A questionnaire survey was used to collect primary data from NSSF mid-level employees during the study. The questionnaire comprised both restricted or closed and unrestricted or open ended questions. The reasons for using open and closed ended questionnaire was to enable the coding process of data in the SPSS program. Questionnaires were pre-tested before being used. The aim was to test whether the questions were understood by the respondents to achieve the research objectives, to test whether the questions are relevant and adequate, to test whether the wording of questions is clear and suit to the understanding of the respondents with different background and to develop appropriate procedure for administering the instrument with reference to field conditions (Rasheed *et al.*, 2021). Also, pre testing was assessing whether the questions are clear, specific, answerable, interconnected and substantially relevant (Arnold and Pfannkuch, 2019). The exercise helped to fine-tune the questionnaire. Some ambiguous questions were removed and others were rephrased. After a pre-test, questionnaires were revised; some questions were rephrased in order to make them more understandable. After revision, questionnaires were duplicated ready for use. The time for pre-testing was about 20 minutes per respondents.

Questionnaires were administered to establish rapport and to explain the purpose of the study as well as to clarify the meaning of the items that may not be clearly as noted by (Willis, 2015). Caronia (2018) defines an interview as a tool, "whose purpose is to gather descriptions of the life-world of the interviewee with respect to interpretation of the meaning of the described phenomena". An interview is a data collection technique that involves oral questioning of respondents either individually or as a group. The answers to the question posed during an interview can be recorded by writing them down either during the interview itself or immediately after the interview or by tape recording the responses or by a combination of both. Interviews can be conducted with varying degrees of flexibility as described by Northridge and Metcalf (2016).

Ren (2016) asserts that, an interview is regarded as an interchange of views between two or more people on a topic of mutual interest and emphasizes the social situations of research data. It is a research instrument for data collection that involves a collection of data through verbal interaction between the interviewee and the interviewer. Patton *et al.*, (2017) argues that, it enables participants to discuss their interpretations of the world in which they live and express how they regard the situation from their own point of view and it is associated with very high response rate. Raya (2018) considers that the general interview guide approach is useful as it 'allows for in-depth probing while permitting the interviewer to keep the interview within the parameters traced out by the aim of the study'. Therefore, in this study in-depth interviews were conducted and the answers were recorded immediately by writing down for further use in the analysis.

Another method used to gather information from the pupils on the challenges they faced as they learnt mathematics was by using a focus group discussion. A focus group is a method whereby a group of six to eight people are brought together to discuss a given event or phenomenon in which they have a shared experience (Gammie *et al.*, 2017). The researcher decided to use a focus group discussion because it is a technique that can be used where individual interviews are too time consuming and too difficult to arrange. It is an economical method of collecting a lot of verbal data. Among its strengths are providing rich and in-depth data and allows the researcher to produce concentrated data on a precise topic (Brinkmann, 2022). The researcher conducted the focus group discussion with the participants using an interview guide with

semi-structured questions. The researcher facilitated the interaction and let the questions guide the discussion by allowing a flexible allocation of time to participants. Hence the researcher was able to explore new directions relevant to the study and allowed a more fluid interaction between the participants as they were given the opportunity to elaborate on each other's answers. A dynamic interaction among the participants was encouraged for the purpose of stimulating their thoughts and all participants, including the researcher had an opportunity to ask questions.

Various methods of data analysis can be used by researchers when they are conducting the research. However, based on the nature of this study and the type of data collected are the major aspects to consider during the time of data analysis (Mukherjee, 2019). Qualitative techniques begin by identifying themes in the data and relationships between themes. The researcher used qualitative technique to analyze data in the form of logical statements and arguments. This is because qualitative research helps people to see the world view of studies concerned. The researcher used qualitative to analyze data, whereby SPSS software package version 20 was used, percentages, tables, charts and histograms was used to summarize the amount of data obtained from the field. Computer program software called Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20 was used. The reason of using SPSS is just because SPSS is a large and powerful general purpose statistical package with excellent data management facilities and high quality graphics (Pituch and Stevens, 2015).

Editing was done so as to eliminate errors that might happen during field data collection and also to identify any inconsistencies in data collection. It is also important to edit data in order to avoid entering wrong data into the computer software since when wrong data are processed, even the end result was wrong (Al-Shallakh *et al.*, 2021). Besides coding is the process of condensing data into smaller units through creation of categories and concepts from data (Li *et al.*, 2022). Validity states whether is the instrument is capable of measuring what is accurate, effective and efficient (Al-Omari *et al.*, 2022). This was achieved through setting standards on constructing questionnaires and interview related to the researcher's objectives and questions. In this study, interview and questionnaires was generated in conjunctions with the researcher. This ensures that the interview guides and questionnaires focused on the topic under investigation and the purpose of the study was clearly explained to the respondents and issues of concerned were resolved satisfactorily. The procedures of interview and questionnaire were explained to the respondents. Lastly, respondents were assured of anonymity and confidentiality, which in turn encouraged frankness during the interview.

Besides that, the type of data collected through questionnaires, interviews, and documentary sources are valid and reliable. The validity and reliability of data was based on the fact that, documentary data were obtained from the already worked data available in schools and those data from the primary source (from pupils). Data from questionnaires will supplement gaps that were occurred due to improper recording of data in documents, since questionnaires allow a particular person to explain what exactly he/she perceives. On the other hand, interviews provide reliable data because they draw data directly from one to be interviewed expressing his/her ideas. All these techniques improved the quality of data and hence its reliability. The above steps helped to ensure that the multiple sources of data collection such as literature, interviews and questionnaires were conducted under conditions and in an environment acceptable to the respondents and therefore ensured that the process and findings are trustworthy and valid. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were ensured so that they enabled to provide information for use strictly for the purpose of the study. A rapport with the respondents was successfully established during the preliminary fieldwork study. The relationship of trust with the respondents was built, the credibility of the study was well be reinforced which was ensured that the discussion level to be high are necessary and relevant to the study.

3. Results and Discussion

This study used stratified random sampling to ensure that the two (2) zones in the western area urban are all represented. Therefore, stratified sampling and simple random sampling techniques was used to select the primary school in the Eastern and Western area of Freetown from which data were collected from pupils, parents and teachers. Schools from each zone had the same chance of being selected. The remaining schools were to be used for pre testing of this research and were not included in the research study. According to Nanjundeswaraswamy and Divakar (2021) a sample size for descriptive study should be between 10 percent to 20 percent of the population. Ten (10) pupils were selected from the selected primary schools, through simple random sampling techniques; also forty (40) parents were selected from the community teachers association (CTA) through simple random sampling techniques, and ten teachers were purposively selected from the selected schools, giving a total of sixty (60) respondents from each school, the number of schools

selected from the two zones (East and West) was five (5), thus the respondents for the each zone is 30 (30 x 2). Therefore the population for this study is 300 subjects and a sample size of 60: Re (20% of 300; the sample size for this study is 60 subjects).

3.1. Household Size of Respondents in Western Area Urban

Figure 1. Household size of respondents in western area urban (Source: Field data, 2024).

Figure 1 above showed the household size of respondents targeted in the study. 43% was made up of parents who lived in households that consisted of 1-4 children; the other group, 44% was made up of parents who lived in households that consisted of 5-9 children; the next largest category was 12% of parents that lived in household of 10-15 children. 1%, the smallest category, belonged to households that had above 15 household children.

3.2. The Effect of the Parents' Level of Education on Pupils' Academic Performance in Public Primary Schools in Western Area Urban District

Figure 2. Parent's level of education in western area urban (Source: Research data, 2024).

In this part of the survey instrument the respondents were asked to rate the effect of the parents' level of education on pupils' academic performance in line with the items in Figure 2. The data indicated that majority of the respondents (33.33%) had secondary education, follow by (21.67%) of the respondents had primary education, another (21.67%) of the respondents were illiterate. 13.33% of the respondents had

vocational education, while (6.67%) of the respondents had secondary education and (3.33%) of the respondents had university education.

3.3. Level of Father Education in Western Area Urban District

Figure 3. Level of father education in western area urban district (Source: Research data, 2024).

The study question asked the level of father education provided the following picture as shown on Figure 3, fathers who are illiterate accounted for (13.33%), those with primary school education accounted for (46.67%) of the respondents. Fathers with secondary school education accounted for (18.33%) of the respondents. Vocational education made (10%) of father's education. College education made (8.33%) of the respondents and parents with university education made (3.33%).

Figure 1, illustrated the influence of extended family ties in the lives of the typical African. Most of these parents were living in overcrowded homes and they find it difficult to meet their physical and emotional needs to support and positively influence the academic performance of pupils in primary schools in the western area urban district. Figure 2 implies that majority of the respondents had only secondary education which may not give them the opportunity to gain lucrative job. It was observed that education of a parent has significance influence on student's performance. Figure 3 shows that majority of the fathers have primary education followed by those with secondary school. However the minority of the fathers possessed university education. The study established that parent's education is likely to influence on pupils' performance in primary schools in western area urban district.

4. Conclusion

The research objective sought to unearth the effect of parents' level of education on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in western area urban. The study targets an estimated number of (60) parents, teachers, and pupils drawn from (5) primary schools in the western area urban. A purposive sampling technique was used to examine the total population of parents, teachers, and pupils in the survey. The study shows that most parents were living in overcrowded homes, and they found it difficult to meet their physical and emotional needs to support and positively influence the academic performance of pupils in primary schools in the western area urban district. The findings further indicated that the majority of the parents had only secondary education. This implies that the education of parents has a significant influence on pupils' academic performance.

5. Recommendations

- 1) The results revealed that the majority of the respondents were in large households. Most of these parents were living in overcrowded homes, and they may find it difficult to meet their physical and emotional needs to support and positively influence the academic performance of pupils. Government should put measures in place to regulate large household size of parents.
- 2) Results revealed that the majority of the respondents had vocational education. The government should provide an adult literacy programme to ensure that parents build their capacity as this will significantly

influence pupils' academic performance. Results revealed that the majority of the respondents were fathers with middle-income earnings. School administrators should encourage fathers with high incomes to give financial support to the underprivileged pupils in the school. Results revealed that majority of the mothers were middle income employees.

- 3) The government should create an enabling environment for all parents to acquire post-secondary education. Teachers should help pupils with problems instead of punishing them. As for parents, they must guide pupils so that they can perform well. Parents must check the exercise books so as to know the progress of the pupils and help them to do their homework.
- 4) The Ministry of Basic and Senior Secondary Education (MBSSE) and the Freetown Municipal Council, should provide remedial adult education classes to improve the skills and knowledge of parents in order to build their capacities. The government through the Ministry of Land Housing and Country Planning should build more affordable houses for parents at a cost recovery that meets the needs of a parent living in overcrowded homes.

Declarations

Acknowledgements: The authors wish to thank Mr. Abdul Foday Kamara, the laboratory technician, and technology expert school for providing the equipment to collect and analyze the data.

Author Contributions: The authors confirm their contribution to the paper as follows: GTP: Study concept and design and proofreading of the work; USF: Data collection and work writing.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Consent to Publish: The authors agree to publish the paper in International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research

Data Availability Statement: Data are contained within the article.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

International Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Research Content: The research content of manuscript is original and has not been published elsewhere.

References

1. Akinbode, O.S. and Olasunkanmi, O.S. 2016. Relationship among socio-economic background, peer group and academic achievement of pupils in public secondary schools in Ogun State. *African Journal of Educational Management*, 17(4): 121-143.
2. Ali, N., Ullah, A., Khan, A.M., Khan, Y., Ali, S., Khan, A. et al. 2023. Academic performance of children in relation to gender, parenting styles, and socioeconomic status: What attributes are important. *Plos One*, 18(11): e0286823.
3. Al-Omari, B., Farhat, J. and Ershaid, M. 2022. Conjoint analysis: A research method to study patients' preferences and personalize care. *Journal of Personalized Medicine*, 12(2): 274.
4. Al-Shallakh, M.A., Azmi, M.N. and Palaming, A.G. 2021. Investigating the syntactic errors faced by Omani learners at the college level: Proposing a self-learning material. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 58(1): 854-873.
5. Anderson, R.E. 2018. And still WE rise: Parent-child relationships, resilience, and school readiness in low-income urban Black families. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 32(1): 60-70.
6. Anthony, W. 2019. The role of parental involvement in their children's education towards pupils' academic performance in primary school: A case of Bahi District, Dodoma-Tanzania. Doctoral Dissertation, Department of Policy Planning and Administration.
7. Arnold, P. and Pfannkuch, M. 2019. Posing comparative statistical investigative questions. In: Burrill, G. and Ben-Zvi, D. (Eds.), *Topics and Trends in Current Statistics Education Research*, ICME-13 Monographs, Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03472-6_8
8. Arthur, L.G. 2022. Parental socio-economic status and academic performance of junior high school pupils in the Ekumfi District. Doctoral Dissertation, University of Education, Winneba.
9. Badore, F.W. 2018. Evaluation of modus operandi as a perpetrator identification technique in the investigation of rape cases. *Forensic Investigation*, University of South Africa.
10. Bakar, N.A., Mamat, I. and Ibrahim, M. 2017. Influence of parental education on academic performance of secondary school students in Kuala Terengganu. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(8): 296-304.

11. Brinkmann, S. 2022. *Qualitative interviewing: Conversational knowledge through research interviews*. Oxford University Press.
12. Caronia, L. 2018. Research interview as social interaction. Epistemic implications. In: Weigand, E. and Kesckes, I. (Eds.), *From pragmatics to dialogue* (83–112). Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
13. Castro, M., Expósito-Casas, E., López-Martín, E., Lizasoain, L., Navarro-Asencio, E. and Gaviria, J.L. 2015. Parental involvement on student academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Research Review*, 14: 33-46.
14. Chen, Q., Kong, Y., Gao, W. and Mo, L. 2018. Effects of socioeconomic status, parent–child relationship, and learning motivation on reading ability. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9: 1297.
15. Das, P. and Tiwari, A. 2023. The impact of mother's education on children's educational outcome: A household level analysis. In: *Inclusive developments through socio-economic indicators: New theoretical and empirical insights* (pp. 307-318). Emerald Publishing Limited.
16. Davis-Kean, P.E., Tang, S. and Waters, N.E. 2019. Parent education attainment and parenting. In: *Handbook of parenting* (pp. 400-420). Routledge.
17. Epstein, J.L. and Sheldon, S.B. 2019. The importance of evaluating programs of school, family and community partnerships. *Aula Abierta*, 48(1): 31-42.
18. Erola, J., Jalonen, S. and Lehti, H. 2016. Parental education, class and income over early life course and children's achievement. *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility*, 44: 33-43.
19. Gammie, E., Hamilton, S. and Gilchrist, V. 2017. Focus group discussions. In: *The Routledge companion to qualitative accounting research methods* (pp. 372-386). Routledge.
20. Hirsch, E.D. 2019. *Why knowledge matters: Rescuing our children from failed educational theories*. Harvard Education Press.
21. Idris, M., Hussain, S. and Ahmad, N. 2020. Relationship between parents' education and their children's academic achievement. *Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, 7(2): 82-92.
22. Kapur, R. 2018. *Research methodology: Methods and strategies*. Department of Adult Education and Continuing Extension, University of Delhi: New Delhi, India.
23. Kiboi, W.N. 2018. *Effect of parental socio-economic status on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Bungoma County, Kenya*. Masters Thesis, Kenyatta University.
24. Kigobe, J., Van den Noortgate, W., Ligembe, N., Ogondiek, M., Ghesquière, P. and Van Leeuwen, K. 2021. Effects of a parental involvement intervention to promote child literacy in Tanzania: A cluster randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness*, 14(4): 770-791.
25. Kikoti, J.V. 2018. *Parents' participation in improving pupils' academic performance in Sumbawanga municipal community secondary schools, Tanzania*. Masters Thesis, The Open University of Tanzania.
26. Lazaro, M. 2023. *The effects of parental involvement on pupils' academic performance in Tanzania: A case of Temeke primary schools, Dar es Salaam, Region*. Masters Thesis, The Open University of Tanzania.
27. Li, I., Pan, J., Goldwasser, J., Verma, N., Wong, W.P. et al. 2022. Neural natural language processing for unstructured data in electronic health records: A review. *Computer Science Review*, 46: 100511.
28. Liu, H. 2015. Explore mother's educational expectations and aspirations: A case from China. *International Journal of Sociology of Education*, 4(2): 128-157.
29. MacDonald, A. 2019. *Increasing father participation in parent education in Prince Edward Island*. Masters Thesis, University of Prince Edward Island.
30. Magnuson, K.A. and Duncan, G.J. 2019. Parents in poverty. *Handbook of parenting*. 3rd Edition, Routledge, 301-328.
31. Malumo, I. 2020. *The role of parents in fostering children's emergent literacy skills in selected rural households of Mongu District, Zambia*. Doctoral Dissertation, The University of Zambia.
32. Mauka, A.M. 2015. *Parental involvement and its effects on pupils' academic performance in public secondary schools in Korogwe, Tanzania*. Doctoral Dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania.

33. Mukherjee, S.P. 2019. A guide to research methodology: An overview of research problems, tasks and methods. CRC Press.
34. Muthomi, S.K. 2019. Influence of selected parental characteristics on children academic performance in public pre-schools in Tigania west sub-county, Meru county, Kenya. Doctoral Dissertation, Africa Nazarene University.
35. Mwakililo, P.S. and Mgaya, A.J. 2021. The influence of parents' involvement in student's academic achievement in community secondary schools in Tanzania-a case of Mbeya City, Tanzania. <http://repository.costech.or.tz/handle/123456789/93960>
36. Nanjundeswaraswamy, T.S. and Divakar, S. 2021. Determination of sample size and sampling methods in applied research. *Proceedings on Engineering Sciences*, 3(1): 25-32.
37. Niklas, F., Cohrssen, C. and Tayler, C. 2016. Parents supporting learning: A non-intensive intervention supporting literacy and numeracy in the home learning environment. *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 24(2): 121-142.
38. Northridge, M.E. and Metcalf, S.S. 2016. Enhancing implementation science by applying best principles of systems science. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 14: 1-8.
39. Núñez, J.C., Epstein, J.L., Suárez, N., Rosário, P., Vallejo, G. and Valle, A. 2017. How do student prior achievement and homework behaviors relate to perceived parental involvement in homework?. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8: 1217.
40. Nzuruba, J. 2024. Parental involvement in child education. *Journal of Language and Culture in Education*, 1(1): 152-172.
41. Onwuegbuzie, A.J. and Collins, K.M. 2017. The role of sampling in mixed methods-research. *The Cologne Journal of Sociology and Social Psychology*, 69(Supplement 2): 133-156.
42. Otieno, T.K. 2019. Socio-economic factors influencing participation of pupils in public primary school education in Mbita Subcounty, Kenya. Doctoral Dissertation, University of Nairobi, Kenya.
43. Paat, Y.F. 2017. The roles of family, neighborhood, and school contextual factors on social work minority pupils' educational aspirations and integration. *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*, 27(3): 232-249.
44. Patton, D.U., Hong, J.S., Patel, S. and Kral, M.J. 2017. A systematic review of research strategies used in qualitative studies on school bullying and victimization. *Trauma, Violence, and Abuse*, 18(1): 3-16.
45. Paweenawat, S.W. 2024. The effect of parental education on children's education and skills in Thailand. *The Singapore Economic Review*, 69(3): 1231-1263.
46. Pituch, K.A. and Stevens, J.P. 2015. Applied multivariate statistics for the social sciences: Analyses with SAS and IBM's SPSS. Routledge.
47. Puccioni, J. 2015. Parents' conceptions of school readiness, transition practices, and children's academic achievement trajectories. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 108(2): 130-147.
48. Rasheed, S., Venkatesh, P., Singh, D.R., Renjini, V.R., Jha, G.K. and Sharma, D.K. 2021. Ecosystem valuation and eco-compensation for conservation of traditional paddy ecosystems and varieties in Kerala, India. *Ecosystem Services*, 49: 101272.
49. Raya, S.T. 2018. Assessment of parental involvement in student's academic performance in Tanzania: The case of public secondary schools in Kinondoni District. Doctoral Dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania.
50. Ren, C.B. 2016. Qualitative research. In: *Encyclopedia of tourism* (pp. 1-4). Springer Publishing Company.
51. Rukwaru, M. 2015. *Social research methods: A complete guide*. Eureka Publishers.
52. Strickland, S. 2015. Effects of parental motivations on home-based and school-based parental involvement. Doctoral Dissertation, Walden University, Minneapolis, Minnesota.
53. Tan, T.X., Zhou, Y. and Li, G. 2020. Maternal education and Chinese first graders' performance in language and literacy and math: Role of home environment. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 48(2): 243-252.
54. Wakiuru, M.M. 2016. Influence of parents' socio-economic status on their participation in children's pre-school education in Kayole, Nairobi County, Kenya. Kenyatta University.

55. Willis, G.B. 2015. Analysis of the cognitive interview in questionnaire design. Oxford University Press.
56. Yahaya, A., Maakip, I., Voo, P., Yusuf, M.Y.M. and Ramli, N.K.B.A. 2020. Effects of self-regulated learning, parental involvement and homework on academic achievement of school students. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 9(2): 327-342.

Citation: George Tony Patrick and Umar Sorie Fofanah. 2024. The Effect of Parents' Level of Education on Pupils' Academic Performance in Public Primary Schools in Western Area Urban District, Sierra Leone. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 8(11): 16-26.

Copyright: ©2024 George Tony Patrick and Umar Sorie Fofanah. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.